

Report: STEM in early childhood education

Introduction

In today's world, technology and the presence of digital tools such as learning apps and websites has hugely impacted the way children learn. With children spending a lot of their time on iPads and digital screens, a lot of market apps have been developed by individuals to cater to children's interests and learning. However, relevancy and functionality of these apps and how they support children's learning is a big question and needs to be asked before introducing any app or website to children.

According to Pohio, (2009), the impact of digital apps and tools on young children is directly related to the role of educators and adults present during these experiences. Thus, it is important that educators/adults choose responsible and meaningful digital apps and tools that not only enhance children's learning but are also age appropriate and safe to use. In this report, three modern teaching STEM apps from worldwide markets will be analysed based on their functionality and relevance to children's learning and safety.

Literature Review: Recent research literature on STEM education.

Children are natural explorers and investigators and have a natural eagerness to understand the functioning theories behind the world around them. STEM which stands for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, is an interdisciplinary approach that combines these four pillars of learning to promote critical thinking skills, creativity, and problem solving skills in children. It is quite relevant and important in early childhood education as it lays foundations for lifelong learning and skills that will help in future school education. According to Smith and Gasser, (2005), STEM concepts foster cognitive development and creative thinking skills among children and support children for future academic success. Zollman, (2012) also states that, "STEM is about questions that can be explored scientifically; or about technological problems that can be solved through engineering and design" (p.1). A study by Katz, (2010), claims that introduction of STEM in early childhood education promotes an environment for children to develop social-emotional skills such as

collaboration, resilience, adaptation and accommodation based on situations and communication with a wider world through exploration and analysis during play.

Australian Government Department of Education [AGDE], (2022) and supporting bodies recognise the importance of STEM in early childhood education in their document 'Being, Belonging and Becoming - Early Years Learning Framework' [EYLF]. Within this document, educators are encouraged to incorporate STEM concepts for children using play based strategies and set ups and promote independence and investigation amongst children to discover science, technological, engineering and maths concepts hidden behind the world around them. Additionally, the Australian Children's Education and Care Quality Authority [ACECQA], 2018, also lays the guidelines of incorporating STEM in children's learning through everyday experiences and interactions promoting hands-on learning and inquiry based approach. Furthermore, to understand how important and beneficial STEM is for young children, An Early Learning STEM Australia Program [ELSA] has been developed by the Department of Education, Skills and Employment, (2019). Within ELSA, educational programs, professional development and effective resources in centres and schools are encouraged to boost STEM learning in early years and primary school years of children. This initiative highlights the positive impact of STEM on learners all around the country.

The use of technology and mobile apps has skyrocketed in recent times, especially among young children (based on data by Smith, 2023). Children have access to technology at homes at all times. Even (United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF], 2017), has recognised that more and more children are living in the digital world and a term called "digital childhoods" emerged from there. Therefore, it is the time for educators to update themselves and develop new skills and strategies to cope up with the changing times and learn how to effectively incorporate these digital tools into children's learning. There may be conflicted opinions on the use of apps in teaching environments such as screen time or loss of physical play, however Research by Pohio, (2009), suggests that if used correctly, mobile apps can enhance learning experiences and support various developmental domains amongst children. For example, Neumann, & Neumann, (2017), found that mobile apps improve early literacy skills such as phonemic awareness, letter recognition, sentence formation in young children. Similarly, these apps can foster motivation engagement through rewards earned in the apps, vibrant designs and characters, challenges and personal experiences that are not found in traditional methods (Smith, 2023). However the quality and the effectiveness of these apps is

highly based on the context in which they are used. Here, caution is recommended to prevent overuse of these apps, digital safety of children and balanced supervised screen times to encourage physical play and social interactions among children (backed by Pohio, 2009).

According to Smith, (2023), for educational apps to be effective, they should be able to align on children's developmental needs and align with pedagogical principles of learning and development. This means that the apps should be able to engage children effectively, provide age appropriate and developmentally appropriate content, inspire creativity and imagination and should encourage parental and educators involvement (p.7-11). If further aligned with EYLF outcomes, it is advisable to introduce apps for children that -

1. Foster a sense of security and safety by strengthening children's sense of identity as they learn about their potential (EYLF outcome 1)
2. Support children in connecting and contributing to the wider world (EYLF outcome 2)
3. Support children in developing a sense of belonging and well-being by fostering optimism (EYLF outcome 3)
4. Support children in becoming confident in exploring, investigating, experimenting, and learn new theories by trial and error. This also aligns very well with science, engineering and technological concepts as children learn better through experiences. (EYLF outcome 4)
5. Support children in developing efficient communication skills (EYLF Outcome 5). [AGDE, 2022].

Based on this information, here are a few apps that support STEM education and learning for young children.

APP 1: Kiddopia, by Kiddopia, Inc. (2010).

Image source: Kiddopia, Inc. 2024.

STEM category: Science, technology, Engineering and maths games based on exploratory concepts. Self expression and creativity are promised skills learnt from the app.

Description: The developers, Kiddopia, Inc. (2010) have promised in this app that children aged 2-7 will be able to enjoy a perfect blend of education and entertainment as children are able to choose from a range of games like problem solving through role playing as different characters, learn about different creatures living in water or land and mathematical skills through game interface.

Relevancy in early childhood environment: The app contributes towards EYLF outcome 4 as it allows children learn different science and mathematical concepts by providing similar to real life experiences, investigating, exploring, trial and error, and roleplaying, (AGDE, 2022). Also, the app introduces different problem based scenarios within their games that allow children to practise creative thinking skills, problem solving, practise social-emotional skills, learn new language terms, and analyse new science concepts and theories.

Pros: The app has promised to include zero ads and features for it to be child safe and friendly. No inappropriate content is promised. User interface is quite child friendly. The graphics and the sounds in the app are very high quality and vibrant, sparking an interest in children. Meehan, (2023), in her review of the app mentions, “Kiddopia offers all the basic concepts of general knowledge in a playful, intuitive way on a small screen, making it an award winning app”.

Cons: The app’s free version has a limited amount of features and requires users to make in-app purchases to access high quality content which may cost upto \$70 a year, making it a bit expensive for a lot of parents.

APP 2: Little Builders, by Fox and Sheep GmbH, (2020)

Source: Fox and Sheep GmbH, 2024

STEM category: Construction, engineering, problem solving.

Description: The app features a range of construction activities for children aged 2-6 years old where they have opportunities to go on different stages, create buildings, mix different materials to construct towers, solving plumbing issues, paint houses and other engineering activities. Besides construction, the app features tiny tasks like water pipes bursting or building blocks falling out and children need to figure out ways to fix it, encouraging creative thinking and problem solving skills.

Relevancy in early childhood environment: The app, as promised to be a great interactive and construction app, has a lot of opportunities for children to test out different engineering theories and learn from their mistakes, strengthening their sense of identity and confidence. Thus, EYLF outcome 1 and 4. This allows children to be more engaged in problem solving tasks, test out trial and error method to effectively learn engineering and construction concepts like stacking, balancing, dimensions, etc. Secondly, since the app has a real life simulation experience, it provides children with an opportunity to know more about real world problems and enact through imagination and role playing real situations. This supports EYLF outcome 2 of connecting and contributing to the world (AGDE, 2022).

Pros: The app provides high quality graphics and user interface making it touch and sensory friendly for toddlers and preschoolers. The animations are quite interesting and engaging with no ads, thus capturing children's attention without interruption. Furthermore, the functions of the game can be customised based on the user's needs like choosing what button performs what task, making it quite easy to use for children requiring additional support.

Cons: The app is not free of charge and requires a certain amount to be paid before downloading. Compared to the costs of the app, there are only a limited amount of tasks and levels in the app which finish very quickly, leaving the user bored.

APP 3: Thinkrolls 1: Puzzles for kids, by Avokiddo Ltd., 2016

Source: Avokiddo Ltd., 2016

STEM category: maths, engineering, technology, logic, reasoning and problem solving.

Description: Thinkrolls is a game based educational app which is divided into two parts - easy mode (for ages 2-5) and hard mode (for ages 5-9). Users choose their game mode based on their age, and create a unique character for themselves that goes on to solve different puzzles, games, quizzes, logical reasoning situations and even build their own puzzles by coding, based on their game level. The app is extensively rich in providing children with opportunities to learn STEM as the developer guarantees 2000+ science and maths games from as simple as shape recognition, numeracy calculations, geometry and patterns to complex tasks like coding self games. The app also promises to push children to use logic and creative thinking skills in solving identical to real life situations from role playing and imagination tasks.

Relevancy in early childhood environment: The app is quite interesting with a lot of features, but the best feature it has is the ability to provide children (the user) with opportunities to create their own unique characters and discover their own paths through logical and critical thinking. This satisfies EYLF learning outcome 1 as children familiarise themselves with their potential and challenge themselves, making them confident in their identities (AGDE, 2022). Furthermore, EYLF outcome 4 is also met via this app as it

encourages children to explore, investigate, analyse, theories, question concepts of science and maths via 207 unique game modes (AGDE, 2022). Moreover, children are learning about concepts of the world around them through games and puzzles rather than a usual learning curriculum. Here, creative thinking, problem solving, sense of relativity, visualising skills, cognitive skills, spatial cognition, memory, observation skills and reasoning skills are enhanced in children.

Pros: Users are given multiple game modes and more than 200 games and tasks, sparking interest and engagement in young children. The user interface and graphics are quite calm and soothing for young children with soft music playing in the background and soft colour options for younger children. If educators use this app, they are able to track at least 9 children's records at one time. The app is quite safe for children as it contains no ads and no in app purchases.

Cons: There is a one time 4€ download charge on the app, which may not be a reasonable charge for a lot of parents for merely 200 games. Due to multiple game options, a child might be too engrossed in the app and may get addicted.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the report focuses on the understanding of STEM and highlights how the world has changed with the digitisation of modern education and the introduction of apps and websites to young children. This is unavoidable because these digital tools are available to children at homes, thus inviting a need for teachers to learn about these tools and incorporate best practices to ensure safe technology use for children. Based on this information, the report analysed what makes a digital app educational and meaningful in teaching children STEM. The given apps have been analysed down to their graphics, STEM learning opportunities and value for money for parents. To summarise, the apps have proven to be quite effective in introducing STEM to young children and their safety and ability to teach children new skills is quite commendable. Although some of these apps may not be free, setting them back for some users. It is recommended for early childhood educators to use these apps in teaching children STEM as it may interest children and make learning fun, however, educators might find it expensive to fund the regular use of these apps.

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Neharika Verma

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